

ON-IT GUIDELINES

FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF
EFFECTIVE ONLINE INTERNSHIPS
IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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More information on the ON-IT project can be found at: www.on-it.info

Table of contents

1.	6	
	Introduction to the project	6
	Introduction to the Guidelines	6
2.	8	
	2.1 Internship, traineeship, WBL, WIL: definition of the terms	8
	2.2 Characteristics of educational internship in higher education	9
	2.3 Online internship or e-internship	10
3.	13	
	3.1 Principles for quality internships	12
	3.2 Procedures to ensure the quality of implementation	12
4.	15	
	4.1 Internship principles and procedures in the countries of the consortium	14
	4.2 Internships principles and procedures in the sample of consulted players	16
5.	20	
	5.1 Proposed framework draft for consultation	18
	5.2 Additional requirements for students with special needs	18
6.	21	
	6.1 Consultation process	19
	6.2 Consultation results	19
	6.2.1 Sample	19
	6.2.2 Preparation phase feedback	19
	6.2.3 Implementation phase feedback	21
	6.2.4 Evaluation phase feedback	21
	6.2.5 General impressions and considerations on the framework	22
	6.3 Revisions following consultation results	23
	References	25

Annex 1. ON-IT Draft Framework for Quality Online Internships	29
Annex 2. Consultation questionnaire	32
Annex 2. ON-IT Final Framework for Quality Online Internships	36

1. The ON-IT Guidelines

Introduction to the project

ON-IT Online Internship in Europe focuses on developing guidelines and resources to design and implement meaningful remote internships in higher education. Starting from both a mapping of experiences from EU institutions and a review of present guidelines for a quality internship, the consortium will draft and test remote work-based learning pathways. The outputs will seek to cover the overall system that allows work-based learning, including advice on admin procedures. With guidance tools, tutorials and guidelines for teachers, tutors (of both sending/receiving institutions), other university staff, and students, the project also intends to develop learning materials for all the involved targets. Learning materials will be addressed to work-based learning and employability. The project aims to focus also on skills development for remote working to provide students with additional employability skills to increase their professional success in a labour market shaped by digital transformation. As a piloting action, ON-IT focuses on the tourism field and aims at providing outputs that are easily transferable to all fields.

The project is implemented by a consortium composed by University of Macerata, Italy (coordinator); University of La Laguna, Spain; JAMK University of Applied Sciences, Finland; Montpellier Business School, France; University of Rijeka, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Croatia; UNIMED - Mediterranean Universities Union, Italy; IGCAT – International Institute of Gastronomy, Culture, Arts and Tourism, Spain.

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Introduction to the Guidelines

The ON-IT Guidelines define procedures for ensuring the quality of online internships based on desk and field research. The process for the definition of Guidelines includes:

- Literature review, including both scientific articles and policy documents
- Analysis and crossing of data with O1's field research
- Formulation of a first draft of the process
- Consultation with an expert audience (e.g., supervisors, former interns, support services representatives, counsellors, etc.)
- Revision of the process according to the feedback and delivery of the final Guidelines for piloting (O3)

Accordingly, this document is organised as follows:

Chapter 2 defines words and meanings according to previous research and identifies a) characteristics of internships in higher education; b) challenges and advantages of online internships as identified by previous research.

Chapter 3 investigates available reference frameworks for quality internships.

Chapter 4 crosses the key elements/criteria with running processes at the universities of the consortium and with data provided by respondents to the O1's survey/interviews.

Chapter 5 defines the framework for the internship of the ON-IT project for consultation with experts.

Chapter 6 reports the consultation process, highlights revisions, and provides the final ON-IT Guidelines for the following piloting phase.

2. Internship and e-internship

2.1 Internship, traineeship, WBL, WIL: definition of the terms

The term "intern" was used first in medical education around the 1920s, referring to students who practice with a physician or a doctor. Internships were special programmes in college education around the 1960s and became widespread in the 1990s, at least in Europe. To have a learning period in work settings is common today. In 2013, the Eurobarometer survey found that 46 per cent of people aged 18 to 35 had undertaken at least one (and often more than one) traineeship. The traineeship was defined as "a limited period of work practice, whether paid or not, which includes a learning and/or a training component" (DGESAI, 2013).

The distinction between "internship" and "traineeship" is unclear. The latter seems to be more used in Europe to define work practices after graduation, while "internship" is more used for work practices carried out during formal education.

The literature identifies three types of internships (Stewart et al., 2018):

1. Work practice periods during formal education programmes, managed by educational institutions.
2. Periods of work experience in the framework of active labour market policies, designed by governments and usually managed by public employment services or other public bodies.
3. Open market internships: a voluntary internship during formal education or after graduation negotiated directly between the intern and the company.

The diffusion of the internship/traineeship has been remarkable in past decades. However, along with the use, the abuse of this instrument led international and national organisations to study the phenomenon, define standards for implementation, and often laws to regulate its implementation. Several policy initiatives and studies have addressed this issue, above all the formulation of the Quality Framework for Traineeship (QFT) by the European Union Council (2014). The QFT, however, covers periods of work practice in the framework of the active labour market policies and those available on the open market, excluding those implemented in the framework of formal education and training and those for accessing specific professions (e.g., teaching, medicine). The reason given is that traineeships in education and training "are in general of better quality, due to the quality assurance by the educational institutions or professional organisations involved" (EC, 2016).

In Europe, higher education institutions included internships - often compulsory for completing the degree programme - around the 1990s. Pushed to include career preparation and embed skills acquisition in their learning programmes, universities considered internship periods as a type of work-based learning (WBL) valuable for career development (Farmaki, 2018). From a pedagogical perspective, internships certainly enable students to acquire practical knowledge or skills that are difficult to obtain in a classroom (Daniels and Brooker, 2016; Moore and Morton, 2017). From a career development perspective, there is a broad acknowledgement of career development skills acquisition benefits, including teamwork, problem-solving, communication, etc. (Kapareliotis et al., 2019, among others). In general, it is also understood that internships facilitate transitions from education to work, even if there is less agreement on this point: they can be seen as a bridge to employment (Silva et al., 2016) or as a form of unpaid work (Grant-Smith and McDonald, 2018), poorly effective for those with disadvantaged background (Klein and Weiss, 2011), and anyway dependent from the reference labour market (Tzanakou et al., 2021).

As mentioned above, work-based learning (WBL) is the umbrella term that encompasses all educational methods that provide students with real-life work experiences (Atkinson, 2016). Sometimes used as synonymous with WBL, work-integrated learning (WIL) is a broader concept as it also includes activities of work simulation not necessarily situated in a real workplace (for example, a joint project with industry during academic courses, consultancy projects, project-based learning etc.) (Atkinson, 2016; Jackson, 2015).

2.2 Characteristics of educational internship in higher education

An internship is characterised by the relation between three main players – the higher education institution, the hosting organisation, and the student. The benefits of organising/doing an internship are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Benefits of the internship for the involved players

Player	Benefit
Higher education institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Student career development (Holyak, 2013) – Increased institution reputation for prospective students (Vélez and Giner, 2015) – Strengthening of ties with corporate world (Gerken et al., 2012)
Hosting organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reduced costs (Rowe et al, 2018; Galloway et al., 2014; Gault et al., 2017) – Additional resources for specific projects that would not be available (Mertz et al., 2014) – Form of pre-recruitment process (Divine et al., 2007) – As trial period of the intern for future job prospects (Elarde and Chong, 2012) – New approaches and methods (Fleming, 1999) – Implementation of corporate social responsibility strategies in large companies (Gold et al., 2020; Cordero et al., 2014) – Contribution to common societal good for smaller companies (Jenkins, 2006; Spence, 2007)
Student	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Academic achievement (Binder et al., 2015) – Improved career prospects (Saniter and Siedler, 2014; Rigsby et al., 2013) – Increased self-reflection skills (Vélez and Giner, 2015) – Job readiness/marketability (Gault et al., 2010; Kim and Park, 2013, Jackson, 2018; Kapareliotis et al., 2019) – Network building (Stanton, 1992) – Development of transversal and soft skills (Zeher and Korte, 2019; Andrew and Highson, 2008, Korte, 2009, among others)

Challenges in internship implementation include:

- different expectations (Sauder et al., 2019)

- difficult competence-based assessment (D'Angelo, 2014; Riccio et al., 2015)
- scarcity of quality internships, inadequate offer (Narayanan et al., 2010)
- inadequate resources of the higher education institution, poor supervising (Kai Wah Chu, 2020)

2.3 Online internship or e-internship

In 2019, an average of 5.4% of employed persons was working from home on a regular basis (Eurostat, 2020¹). In 2020, following the pandemic emergency, the average of teleworkers increased to 12.0%. According to the Eurofound survey (2021), there will be "No looking back" to telework after that experience: most surveyed employees would prefer a combination of working from home and working from the office; 32% of them would like "to work from home several times a week" (p. 43).

As work changes, WBL also changes. The virtual internship, or online internship, or e-internship started to be implemented about ten years ago (van Dorp et al., 2008; Vriens et al., 2010), but increased dramatically during the Covid-19 pandemic (De Giorgi and Stefanelli, 2021).

So far, research has mostly focused on the intern's experience (Gill, 2020; Irwin et al., 2021). After the emergency of the pandemic, the speed of the online internship development increased the research on this topic. Online internships present additional challenges in comparison to in-office internships, as well as some advantages, as summarised in Table 2.

¹ Table "Employed persons working from home as a percentage of the total employment, by sex, age and professional status (%)[lfsa_ehomp]", Eurostat. Website: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfsa_ehomp

Table 2. Specific challenges and advantages in online internships

Player	Challenges	Advantages
Higher education institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Supervisor's training (Frank and Oliver, 2012) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased learning offer
Hosting organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Organisational issues (IT equipment) (Irwin et al., 2021) – Recruitment of e-intern, particularly for culture/business culture (Jeske and Axtell, 2014; 2018) – Trust building (Irwin et al., 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reduced costs – Opportunity to increase diversity in organisations (Kraft et al. 2019; Jeske and Axtell, 2018)
Student	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Difficult work-life balance (Allan et al., 2015; Charalampous et al., 2019) – Organisational issues (e.g., digital skills in using IT) (Irwin et al., 2021) – High self-regulated learning needed (Dabbagh and Kitsantas, 2004) – Feeling of isolation, disconnection (Teng, 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reduced costs – Opportunity to being part of an international learning community (Ruggiero and Boehm, 2016) – Flexibility of time (Vriens et al., 2010)

There are few models of online internships in higher education.

Lansu et al. (2009) designed and piloted the Virtual Environmental Consultancy (VEC) model at the Open Universiteit Nederland. The VEC allows students to carry out real projects for market clients working in virtual teams, coached by an academic lecturer.

Ruggiero and Bohem (2016) also used a communication platform, Blackboard Virtual Learning Environment, to link the interns, all students in IT, the clients and the academic supervisor working on a consultancy project. The process included the following tasks: 1) participation in weekly discussions in an online learning management system; 2) communication about their internship experience through weekly journal posts; 3) attendance at a minimum of two of the three web conferences during the term; 4) completion of an online evaluation of the internship; 5) submission of a storyboard, usability test, and final video showcasing their redesigned module (p. 110).

Roy and Sykes (2017) based their work on Zopiatis & Constanti's (2012) conceptual framework for best practices in a hospitality internship to design a virtual internship in the same field. The programme phases, articulated in several activities and tasks, are: 1) planning, which includes formal duties such as the agreement and preparation for the internship through learning modules; 2) self-regulation component, in which the student seeks an internship opportunity; 3) engagement stage, in which all involved subjects maintain a journal and log of activities; 4) assimilate, which provides both learnings in the classroom and the virtual internship environment by applying theory to practice; 5) review and reflect, which includes a post-internship seminar as a classroom activity or a one-to-one reflection session.

Furthermore, in 2019, Jeske provided a set of recommendations to design virtual internships for hosting companies, suggesting to:

- Prepare equipment and training carefully to enable the intern to work effectively
- Appoint committed staff available to engage with interns frequently
- Define expectations clearly
- Compensate interns, "treating and paying them fairly"
- Connect internships with diversity initiatives.

3. Quality principles comparison

3.1 Principles for quality internships

The starting point for the identification of quality standards for an educational internship is the European Quality Charter on Internships and Apprenticeships, provided by the ErasmusIntern.org initiative from the European Student Network (ESN).

Article 2 of the Charter states:

We believe that internships (as part of higher education) and apprenticeships should meet the following criteria:

- existence of a written and legally binding contract between the educational institution, intern/apprentice and hosting organisation outlining the main principles of the internship/apprenticeship, including how many credit points this will contribute to the diploma of the intern/apprentice; a description of learning objectives and tasks should be attached to the contract;
- length and tasks of the internship/apprenticeship correspond to specified learning objectives that are shared with the student at the beginning of his/her internship/apprenticeship;
- guidance throughout the internship/apprenticeship period by a supervisor(s) trained specifically for the role;
- the right of the intern/apprentice to receive reimbursement of costs incurred during the internship/apprenticeship or right to receive food, housing, and public transportation tickets instead;
- decent remuneration for work carried out additional to the requirements outlined in the internship/apprenticeship contract, including compensation for overtime;
- clear evaluation criteria of the internship/apprenticeship period.

Further, the ILO (2018) compared a set of countries on the provisions for internship and traineeship, noticing that for educational internships regulations are set as in Table 3.

Table 3. European countries and the UK analysed by Steward et al., 2018

EQIA principles	UK	France	Romania
Written agreement	x	x	x
Tasks/length accorded to learning objectives	x	x	x
Ongoing guidance	x	x	x
Trained supervisor	N/A	N/A	N/A
Reimbursement of costs	-	N/A	-
Remuneration	-	(*)	-
Clear evaluation criteria	N/A	N/A	x

(*) Depends on the duration of the internship. If it is shorter than 44 days, there is no obligation to pay the intern. If the internship is longer than 44 days, then the remuneration shall be about 550 euros (gross) per month (paid from the beginning). For apprenticeship, it depends on the level of the apprentice and the year of apprenticeship. It varies between 700 and 1650 euros per month.

3.2 Procedures to ensure the quality of implementation

Official guidelines and recommendations or national laws, are limited to the definition of principles and minimum standards for the internships: implementation still depends on higher education institutions that, according to educational systems, usually have autonomy in defining procedures and internal regulations for learning provision.

Some previous work carried out in the framework of European funded projects can support the definition of quality procedures for internships: the SPRINT² project and the CAPQUI³ project are examples of the effort of the European community to ensure the quality of work-based learning experiences.

An internship programme can be divided into three main phases – Preparation (pre), Implementation (ongoing), Evaluation (post). Each of the phases entails different tasks. Typically, the three players involved in the programme are the student, the academic supervisor and the company supervisor. The organisations involved are the sending organisation (higher education institution) and the hosting organisation (public, private, for-profit or not). The fourth player, usually not mentioned in the literature, but relevant in actual organisations' processes, is represented by the support services – the career counsellor or administrative officer, who manage part of the process. An additional figure can be the coordinator of the internship programme, who can usually act at the Faculty/Department level and might be in charge of carrying out some process steps. Table 4 summarises the main phases of an internship (tasks that can be performed by different players depending on the organisation in square brackets).

Table 4. Internship phases, tasks and roles

Players	PREPARATION (tasks)	IMPLEMENTATION (tasks)	EVALUATION [tasks]
Student	To apply for an internship position To participate in training/preparation To define (and then accept) the learning plan	Learning on the job To fulfil appointed tasks To keep track of the process (self-reflect and provide monitoring data)	To reflect on evaluation results To evaluate the experience
Academic supervisor or Programme coordinator	[To support matching between the intern and the hosting organisation]	To monitor learning	To assess learning acquisition

² SPRINT – Standardize best practices about internships: <https://www.sprint-erasmusplus.fr/>

³ CAPQUI https://uni-foundation.eu/uploads/2018_report_on_quality_internships.pdf

	[To provide training/preparation to the internship] To define learning outcomes with the student and the hosting organisation		
Company supervisor	To define learning outcomes with the student and the hosting organisation	To support the intern To mentor the intern	To evaluate the intern To reflect on evaluation results
Support service of sending organisation (e.g., career service, internship services, etc.)	[To support matching between the intern and the hosting organisation] [To provide training/preparation to the internship] To provide formal agreements and insurance	To manage tools and data to monitor the internship	To collect evaluation data To provide feedback on evaluation results to involved players

4. ON-IT experience

4.1 Internship principles and procedures in the countries of the consortium

In the experience of the ON-IT consortium, principles of the Quality Charter on Internships and Apprenticeships apply as in Table 5.

Table 5. Principles of QUIA in the countries of the ON-IT consortium

EQIA principles	Croatia	Finland	France	Italy	Spain
Written agreement	x	x	x	x	x
Tasks/length accorded to learning objectives	x	x	x	x	x
Ongoing guidance	x	x	x	x	x
Trained supervisor (with specific course)	x	-	x		
Reimbursement of costs	-	-	-	-	-

Remuneration	-	-	-	-	-
Clear evaluation criteria	-	-	-	-	x

Reimbursement of costs and remuneration are not defined by law in some countries (for example, Italy) but depend on the hosting organisations.

On the procedural side, there are remarkable differences among the involved institutions, as summarised in Table 6, following differences in the personnel profiles and their roles.

At the University of Macerata (UNIMC), Italy, the internship process directly involves:

- Administrative and technical staff: they manage agreements, insurance, legal provisions, monitoring (timesheets) and recording of the experience, including the collection of final evaluation data; they additionally provide online opportunities in a devoted webpage of the website.
- Academic supervisor: usually, professors, who contribute to the formulation of the learning plan and approve it, monitor the process from a pedagogical point of view.
- Delegate for internships: appointed at degrees level, approves the final evaluation of the internships, checking that all requirements have been fulfilled.
- Company supervisor.

At the University of La Laguna (ULL), Spain, the internship process directly involves:

- Career service: they look for companies, prepare and sign agreements between companies and the University and regulate the normative for internships.
- Coordinator of the internship programme who is a professor of the Faculty of Tourism and that matches teachers and students, coordinates the preparation of the internship, and signs the agreement between the student and the company.
- University tutor, a teacher of the Faculty of Tourism who should monitor the internship process and evaluate the student.
- Company tutor, who coordinates and evaluates the internship from the company side.

At the JAMK University, Finland, the internship process directly involves:

- University supervisor: Before the internship, the university supervisor schedules and organises the entire internship process, particularly regarding deadlines, and assignments of students to companies. The university supervisor takes care of signing the contract among the student, company and university. During the internship, he/she follows up on the experience and resolves incidents, if they occur. After the internship, he/she manages the evaluations and closings with students and company supervisors.
- Company supervisor: Before the internship, the company supervisor presents the internship offer and plans it together with the student. During the internship, he/she follows up with the student and the university supervisor, as well as resolves any incident that might arise with them. After the internship, he/she evaluates the student and gives the "internship certificate" after a final discussion at the company.

At the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Management (FTHM), Croatia, the internship process directly involves:

- Academic supervisor/coordinator (professor on faculty) who sets the learning plan for the internship, seeks out companies, manages the agreements between companies and faculty, matches students and companies, coordinates the internship preparation, oversees the internship process, communicates with the company tutor, monitors student and company tutor experiences, collects final evaluation data from students and company tutors, prepares the final internship report for the academic year.
- Company tutor: coordinates and evaluates the students during their internship from the company side.

At the Montpellier Business School (MBS), the internship process depends on the programme (Bachelor, Master, MSc). Overall, it directly involves:

- Career service: they help students clarify their professional experience, provide them with tools to find an internship, follow the contract process, follow up with the students during and at the end of the internship, find solutions should an issue arise between students and companies.
- MBS tutor: a teacher of the Faculty who monitors the internship process and evaluates students.
- Company tutor, who coordinates and evaluates the internship from the company side.

Table 6. Internship procedures in the higher education institution of the ON-IT consortium (main appointed persons – the procedures can vary in specific cases, e.g., the student needs support to find the position).

Tasks	FTHM	JAMK	MBS	UNIMC	ULL
To search for internship positions (main responsible)	Coordinator	Student	Student	Student	Coordinator
To apply for internship positions	Student / Coordinator	Student	Student	Student	Student/ Coordinator
To define the learning plan	Coordinator Company Supervisor Student	Supervisor Student	Supervisor Student	Supervisor Company Student	Academic Supervisor Company supervisor Student
To prepare the intern (orientation and training)	N/A	Coordinator	Support services	Support services	Coordinator
To fulfil admin duties (formal agreements, insurance)	Coordinator	Coordinator	Support services	Support services	Coordinator

To monitor the internship (records of attendance)	Coordinator Company supervisor	Coordinator Company supervisor	Support services	Support services Company supervisor	Company supervisor Company supervisor
To hold mid-term or ongoing meetings/mandatory (monitoring purposes)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
To evaluate the experience	Student Company Supervisor/ Coordinator	Student Supervisor/ Coordinator Company	Student Supervisor/ Coordinator Company	Student Supervisor Company	Student Supervisor/ Coordinator Company

The process did not change in the case of online internships (perhaps some tools have been modified to be available online, as in the case of UNIMC).

In general, it can be noted that the internship process followed by the members of the ON-IT consortium is highly regulated and follows regular procedures. Furthermore, despite the differences among countries, it appears to be almost the same in fundamentals. Some differences can be identified by comparing the universities' procedures and expectations set by previous research for a quality internship.

1. Finding the internship position

In some cases, it is the student who searches for the opportunity: in this case, the university supports them by providing lists of available companies or internship offers, but it does not intervene in the process until the student has found a place. It is a process similar to the job search. The university plays the role of an informant about opportunities, as an employment office, and supports the student with career service offers, such as workshops about CV writing or how to manage an interview. In other cases, the university receives the job offers from the hosting organisations and matches the students with the companies. The role of the student, in this case, is to accept or not the position, and in some cases to propose an alternative internship (acting as a jobseeker).

2. Preparation for the internship

Preparation for the internship seems to be usually carried out within the general career development services, from orientation to participation, to training for specific job-related purposes. To some extent, it could be that a non-formalised training takes place between the supervisor and the student when the learning programme is drafted.

3. Training of supervisors

In all cases, the supervisor is a professor, then a teacher, appointed to monitor and support learning on the job. There is no evidence of a specific training for teachers to support internships.

4. Monitoring of the internship

All universities involved perform some type of monitoring on the internship process. The tools can differ, and an intermediate evaluation can be available or not, depending on the length of the

internship. It is unclear how the academic supervisor supports the learning process during the internship: while for the student, the monitoring is mandatory, even only for attendance to the hosting organisation premises, the supervisors seem not to have required tasks in this respect.

5. Relations with the company

Hosting organisations can have direct relations with the internship/career offices to offer their internship opportunities, with the supervisors, or both. In some cases, options are managed at the Degree level, with staff appointed to the task (usually a professor coordinating the programme for the Degree or the Department/Faculty). Company supervisors, or tutors, can directly contact the people appointed by the university or be managed by the company, particularly if the hosting organisation is large enough to have an HR unit. The preparation of the company supervisor is therefore unclear, and his/her training is appointed to the hosting organisation.

4.2 Internships principles and procedures in the sample of consulted players

According to the research work carried out in the framework of the ON-IT project (De Giorgi and Stefanelli, 2021), principles and procedures of the virtual internships carried out during the pandemic emergency were affected by some difficulties in each step of the process mentioned above.

1. Finding the internship position

This aspect can be assessed only partially since lockdowns in all countries were too sudden, and both sending and hosting organisations had no plans, or were not equipped, to offer positions to all students. In addition, the different management processes of the internship (e.g., university matching offers and profiles, or the student seeking a position autonomously) put pressure on the involved subjects to different extents.

2. Preparation

Data revealed incomplete learning agreements, not fully developed for online work, mostly in tasks and skills development.

3. Training of supervisors

The sample of respondents reported a problematic involvement of the academic supervisors in regular meetings with the company, and in general, low attention to the internship process.

4. Monitoring

Also, in this case, the monitoring of the process, particularly by the university side, was perceived as weak. Some interns reported a feeling of isolation.

5. Relations with the company

Interns perceived the virtual internship as underrated both by companies and universities compared to face-to-face pathways. In addition, there were equipment problems for some, in terms of hardware, software, and internet connection.

Although these inputs must be read with the emergency lens due to the pandemics, some critical points were identified that should be considered in the ON-IT framework development.

5. ON-IT proposed framework of reference

5.1 Proposed framework draft for consultation

The ON-IT framework of reference, based on the previous literature analysis and context (European and at the organisation's level), follows the phases of the process and applies the quality principles to F2F, blended and online internships.

1. Preparation phase

- 1.1. Seeking an internship position
- 1.2. Learning agreement (definition of the learning outcomes, definition of tasks)
- 1.3. Administrative and formal requirements fulfilment, including detailed monitoring procedure and used tools for the purpose
- 1.4. Preparation for the internship (students)
- 1.5. Preparation for the internship (supervisors)

2. Implementation phase

- 2.1. Beginning of the internship
- 2.2. Monitoring according to the defined procedure (includes intermediate evaluation according to the length of the internship, bilateral meetings with supervisors, joint meetings with supervisors)
- 2.3. Closing of the internship

3. Evaluation phase

- 3.1. Formal evaluation and assessment of the internship by the student and the supervisors
- 3.2. Guided self-reflection exercise by the student
- 3.3. Focus group by academic supervisors (once a semester) reporting and reflecting about the internships process carried out to the date, and revision/update of processes and tools.

Full description is available as Annex 1.

5.2 Additional requirements for students with special needs

Students with special needs face additional challenges in work-based learning process implementation, as in the following work insertion. The proposed framework of reference, therefore, although devising the same process, specifies specific tasks that should be considered when the intern has a special need/impairment.

Annex 1 includes a column in which the additional tasks are described.

6. Framework revision after consultation

6.1 Consultation process

The consultation was carried out between February and March 2022 in the organisations of the consortium, as in Table 6, by means of an online questionnaire, provided as Annex 2.

6.2 Consultation results

6.2.1 Sample

Table 7 summarises the profile of respondents:

Table 7. Respondents' profile

Profile	HR	ES	FR	IT	FI	Total
Academic supervisor	2	3	3	6	1	15
Career counsellor	2	0	2	0	1	5
Internship officer	0	0	0	1	2	3
Coordinator/delegate	1	2	0	0	1	4
Company supervisor	0	1	0	0	0	1
Other (*)	0	1	0	1	0	1
Total respondents	5	7	5	8	5	30

() ES respondent: executive expert; IT respondent: associate professor*

6.2.2 Preparation phase feedback

Skills to prepare students before the internship (content)

Skills to prepare students before the ONLINE internship (content)

Content for supervisors' training

Management of relations with the hosting organisations about internship opportunities, excluding administrative procedure (appointed profile) – Y/N (for each respondent)

6.2.3 Implementation phase feedback

Frequency of monitoring

6.2.4 Evaluation phase feedback

What to assess

How to assess

6.2.5 General impressions and considerations on the framework

Suggested changes and need for details

To add	To detail
How do companies provide job and recruiting opportunities? How and who between the student, university, teacher... selects suitable internship partners and opportunities? Are there any requirements needed for that? (Coordinator, FI)	Indicators on career guidance (Career counsellor, HR)
The area in which the supervisor's company operates or the disciplinary scientific field of the academic supervisor (Academic supervisor, IT)	How are the internship offers delivered, collected or communicated to students? How can the matching be done by the university? Before the interview, students need to have some learning materials to be prepared for the interview in the modules (Coordinator, FI)
Explicit links between the courses' theoretical content, the practical learning at the university (laboratories) and the internship (Academic supervisor, IT)	Digital documents and digital signatures (Internship officer, FI)
Online integration follow-up to be completed by the company and the student during the first month of the internship to ensure a good start (Career counsellor, FR)	Evaluation and monitoring (feedback) by the company supervisor (Academic supervisor, FR)

To add	To detail
This perspective could stress the attention on the importance of the process to be monitored by: academic side, job market side and the student involved (Academic supervisor, IT)	Perhaps the research side of the internship. Will the student apply scientific methods in their internship experience? Or is the internship completely detached from the scientific process? (Academic supervisor, FR)
	Probably the last phase could have more details (Associate professor, IT)
	More explicit links between theoretical and practical knowledge (Academic supervisor, IT)

Other comments:

- Preparation of the student: I think it is important to have individual times as well as collective times (Career counsellor, FR)
- The selected host company tutors should have some kind of standardised procedure agreed upon by the University representative to gradually provide the trainee with knowledge (Executive experts, ES)
- Is the practical training paid or not, does it matter? (Internship officer, FI)
- The University can propose good options, only if the student has already given his/her profile and goals. This step is at the beginning of the preparation. (Internship officer, IT)
- The university provides the student with special equipment (Career counsellor, FR)
- I do not think there are aspects that should be better detailed, but I think that some indicators should be adapted to each institution procedure, such as the structure of the learning agreement or the preparation phase in general, e.g. "The university proposes at least two positions to the student" (in my university there is a general list of open positions) (Academic supervisors, IT)
- The responsibility of students about the process should be increased (Internship officer, FI)

6.3 Revisions following consultation results

The ON-IT partners analysed the answers of the consulted experts by sharing them on the online repository of the consortium, and in the framework of a devoted session during the hybrid project meeting that took place in Macerata, IT/online on April 21st, 2022.

Summary of decisions and considerations on the remarks:

- Universities have very different processes and procedures for the implementation of internships, therefore the process, to be applicable in a large number of institutions, cannot go into too much detail: however, some more detailed sub-frames of usage could be detailed in the Intern Guide and Supervisor Guide;
- There is an issue of sustainability and appointment of tasks, which also depends on the involved profiles and the running processes – this applies particularly to the preparation and assessment phases, which should be simplified and made as usable for all as possible, by guaranteeing anyway the quality of the process;
- There is uncertainty about the preparation phase in relation to skills and competences to be developed: the piloting phase would support the understanding of the needs of the interns.

To this aim, a round of interviews specifically focused on the process, with particular attention on the preparation phase, should be planned;

- Awareness on the theoretical-practical links is crucial to the meaning of the internship: therefore, the protocol for self- or guided reflection should include this point;
- The learning outcomes of the internships and the tasks, should be agreed among the players, therefore, the framework cannot include specific provisions on content, or software, or any other detail.

Modifications and clarifications on the framework are provided in red in Annex 3.

Details related to different processes – by field, by running organisation of staff and administrative procedures, etc., should be included in the Intern and Supervisors' Guides in the field of O3.

The feedback from the involved players within the process should be collected at the end of the piloting, and the framework here presented in Annex 2 should be revised according to results.

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Annex 1. ON-IT Draft Framework for Quality Online Internships

Phase	Process	Indicators	Descriptors	Additional requirements/special needs
Preparation	Seeking an internship position (matching by the university)	The university proposes at least two positions to the student	The university should provide the student with the opportunity to choose between two or more options; the process takes place online (including interview)	The university performs assessment tests for evaluating potential and specify special needs in terms of support
	Seeking an internship position (student as a jobseeker)	The student achieves at least one interview	The student is responsible for managing own career progression and should give evidence of his/her ability to surf the labour market	Support is provided to job search (or) Not applicable
	Learning agreement (LA)	The LA includes appointed tasks The LA describes learning outcomes The LA specifies evaluation criteria	The LA is consistent with the internship aims (according to the degree); the LA states each step of the process and it is known by all involved players; the formulation process is carried out online	-
	Admin and formal requirements	The admin/formal requirements are fulfilled before the beginning of the internship Student and hosting organisation are provided with a copy of the documents	The admin and formal requirements are compliant with national and organisational regulations Students are provided with a document summarising the duty of	-

			<p>monitoring and recording; descriptions of tools used are included in the document; the document is also digital</p> <p>Hosting organisations supervisors are provided with a document summarising the duty of monitoring and recording; description of tools used are included in the document; the document is also digital</p>	
	Preparation of the student to the internship	At least one learning programme (modules, materials, calendar) is available for students at least at the beginning of each semester	At the beginning of each semester an online learning course is organised to prepare for the internship; the course is also available online; the course is completed with learning modules related also to online internship.	-
	Preparation of the supervisors to the internship	<p>The learning programme for supervisors is available at the beginning of the academic year</p> <p>Academic supervisors follow the programme at least once per year</p> <p>Hosting company supervisors have the opportunity to undertake a learning programme (optional)</p>	The learning programmes include both procedural and pedagogical subjects; they are available online.	Meetings are held between support services and supervisors to share specific needs of the student
Implementation	Beginning of the internship	Involved players know the procedures	Procedures are fully implementable online.	The university provides the student with special equipment (e.g., assistive technologies)

		The tools for communication and monitoring are ready by the starting date The intern is fully equipped to carry out appointed tasks		
	Monitoring	The learning process is monitored	The monitoring process can take place also online in all its parts	Daily/weekly support may be necessary according to the intern needs; specific tools to record the process may be used
	Closing	Involved players know the procedures for closure of the experience	The monitoring process can be closed online	-
Evaluation	Formal evaluation and assessment	The procedures include evaluation and assessment forms for involved players	All players have access to online tools	-
	Student self-reflection	The student (former intern) is guided in self-reflection of the learning experience	The self-reflection can take place also in group, and always available also online	-
	Supervisor self-reflection	Academic supervisors participate in joint self-reflection meetings at least once per year Hosting company supervisors participate in joint self-reflection meetings at least once per year (optional)	The meetings have the format of focus groups to reflect and plan forward (identify critical points and adjust procedures and processes)	Other professional profiles involved in the process (e.g., special support tutors) should participate the meeting

Annex 2. Consultation questionnaire

Dear expert,

The ON-IT project aims at designing, developing and implementing a framework for ensuring the quality of online internships.

We kindly ask you to provide your feedback, by answering the questions below after having checked the ON-IT draft framework that you can find here below as Annex.

By answering this questionnaire, you agree that your responses will be used as data by the ON-IT project for reporting and research purposes only. The data will not be shared with third parties nor used for commercial purposes. Your personal details and data will be handled following the GDPR guidelines.

Thank you in advance for your contribution!

This survey is also available online at <https://forms.gle/LNtztsE6n2Syf2UJ8>

Something about you

Gender/sex

- Female
- Male
- I prefer not to declare

Country

My profile in relation to internship

- Academic supervisor
- Company supervisor
- Internship officer (or other profile related to admin management)
- Career counsellor or other profile related to career development
- Coordinator or delegate for internships at the Faculty/Department or Programme coordinator/delegate at central university level
- Entrepreneur or working in HR in a company (not supervisor)
- Other

If you have chosen Other, please describe your profile in relation to internships

1. General impressions

1.1 Is there anything missing in the proposed process? Please indicate what should be added, in your opinion.

1.2 What should be better detailed?

2. Preparation phase

2.1 Which skills should be addressed to prepare the students for job/placement search before the internship? Please rate the following items on the scale 1 = not important at all; 5 = very important

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Curriculum vitae drafting					
Motivation letters writing					
Online job/placement search					
Online job interviews					
Ability to identify learning outcomes to define the programme with the hosting organisation and the academic supervisor or programme coordinator					

Do you have any suggestions about this topic? Please use the following space to share your advice/comments.

2.2 Which topics should be included in a course programme to prepare the students for an online internship? Please rate the following items on the scale 1 = not important at all; 5 = very important

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Online communication					
Training on most common online job tools for sharing and communication (e.g., MS Teams, Zoom, Blackboard, Google Meet, etc.)					
Time management					
Online team work					
Online collaboration tools (editing, calendar, tasks management....)					
Life-work balance in telework					
Gender equality and telework (e.g., family time)					

Do you have any suggestions about this topic? Please use the following space to share your advice/comment.

2.3 Which topics should be included in a course programme to prepare supervisors for an online internship? Please rate the following items on the scale 1 = not important at all; 5 = very important

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Online tutoring/mentoring					
Online monitoring and online feedback					
Motivating the online intern/team building					
Career guidance					

Do you have any suggestions about this topic? Please use the following space to share your advice/comment.

2.4 In your opinion, who should manage relations with the hosting organisations about internship opportunities? [not administrative procedures]

Item	Yes	No
Support services, like career centres, internship offices etc.		
The internship coordinator of the Faculty, Department or Degree Programme		
The academic supervisor (professors, lecturers, other academic staff appointed)		
A devoted professional profile at Faculty/Department/Degree Programme level		
A devoted professional at university level		
Other		

If you have chosen 'Other' please explain here below who should be appointed to manage relations with the hosting organisation for internship opportunities

3. Implementation phase

3.1 What should be the frequency of the monitoring activities? Choose the best option among the proposed ones, or choose 'none of the above' then write your ideal monitoring feedback.

Item	Yes	No
Feedback by the intern on shared software/online tool once a week		
Feedback by the intern on shared software/online tool every two weeks		
Feedback by the intern on shared software/online tool once a month		
Feedback by the intern on shared software/online tool at midterm		
Feedback by the intern only on request		
Online meetings between the intern and the supervisor/appointed tutor once a week		
Online meetings between the intern and the supervisor/appointed tutor every two weeks		
Online meetings between the intern and the supervisor/appointed tutor once a month		
Online meetings between the intern and the supervisor/appointed tutor at midterm		
Online meetings between the intern and the supervisor/appointed tutor only on request		
None of the above		

If you have chosen 'none of the above', please describe your ideal monitoring process:

4. Evaluation phase

4.1 Besides practical arrangements evaluation by the involved players (student, academic supervisor/tutor, company supervisor), what is important to evaluate/assess in your opinion? Please rate the following items on the scale 1 = not important at all; 5 = very important; please consider the following items for all the three respondents (i.e., supervisors represent the point of view of the university/hosting organisation)

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Achievement of the learning outcomes					
Work readiness					
Transversal and soft skills					
Perceived usefulness of the programme for learning purposes					
Perceived usefulness of the programme for career purposes					

Do you have any suggestions about this topic? Please use the following space to share your advice/comment.

4.2 Which is the best tool for evaluation/assessment purposes of an online internship from the university perspective? Please rate the following items on the scale 1 = very bad; 5 = very good.

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Online test					
Online group meetings, with more than one student/intern					
Online F2F meetings					
Online survey for students					
Online survey for company supervisors					
Reports by the interns and both supervisors					
In addition to meetings with students/interns: separate meetings with the company supervisors					

Do you have any suggestions about this topic? Please use the following space to share your advice/comment.

Annex 3. ON-IT Final Framework for Quality Online Internships

Revisions/additions in red.

Phase	Process	Indicators	Descriptors	Additional requirements/special needs
Preparation	(Case 1) Seeking an internship position (matching by the university)	The university proposes at least two positions to the student	The university should provide the student with the opportunity to choose between two or more options; the process takes place online (including interview)	The university performs assessment tests for evaluating potential and specify special needs in terms of support
	(Case 2) Seeking an internship position (student as a jobseeker)	The student achieves at least one interview	The student is responsible for managing own career progression and should give evidence of his/her ability to surf the labour market	Support is provided to job search (or) Not applicable
	Learning agreement (LA)	The LA includes appointed tasks The LA describes learning outcomes The LA specifies evaluation criteria	The LA is consistent with the internship aims (according to the degree); the LA states each step of the process and it is known by all	-

			involved players; the formulation process is carried out online	
	Admin and formal requirements	The admin/formal requirements are fulfilled before the beginning of the internship Student and hosting organisation are provided with a copy of the documents	The admin and formal requirements are compliant with national and organisational regulations Students are provided with a document summarising the duty of monitoring and recording; descriptions of tools used are included in the document; the document is also digital Hosting organisations supervisors are provided with a document summarising the duty of monitoring and recording; description of tools used are included in the document; the document is also digital	-
	Preparation of the student to the internship	At least one learning programme (modules, materials, calendar) is available for students at least at the beginning of each semester	At the beginning of each semester an online learning course is organised to prepare for the internship; the course is also available online; the course is completed with learning modules related also to online internship.	-
	Preparation of the supervisors to the internship	The learning programme for supervisors is available at the beginning of the academic year	The learning programmes include both procedural and pedagogical subjects; they are available online.	Meetings are held between support services and supervisors to share specific needs of the student

		Academic supervisors follow the programme at least once per year Hosting company supervisors have the opportunity to undertake a learning programme (optional)		
Implementation	Beginning of the internship	Involved players know the procedures The tools for communication and monitoring are ready by the starting date The intern is fully equipped to carry out appointed tasks	Procedures are fully implementable online.	The university provides the student with special equipment (e.g., assistive technologies)
	Monitoring	The learning process is monitored at least at mid-term	The monitoring process can take place also online in all its parts.	Daily/weekly support may be necessary according to the intern needs; specific tools to record the process may be used
	Closing	Involved players know the procedures for closure of the experience	The monitoring process can be closed online	-
Evaluation	Formal evaluation and assessment	The procedures include evaluation and assessment forms for involved players	All players have access to online tools	-
	Student self-reflection	The student (former intern) is guided in self-reflection of the learning experience The protocol for self-reflection includes analysis of links between theoretical and practical knowledge	The self-reflection can take place also in group, and always available also online The exercises are based on given protocols (common to F2F internships) and contain an additional topic related to the	-

			online work implications between theoretical and practical knowledge	
	Supervisor self-reflection	Academic supervisors participate in joint self-reflection meetings at least once per year Hosting company supervisors participate in joint self-reflection meetings at least once per year (optional)	The meetings have the format of focus groups to reflect and plan forward (identify critical points and adjust procedures and processes)	Other professional profiles involved in the process (e.g., special support tutors) should participate the meeting